

E-STEAM Education

Dr. Munir Moosa coined the term E-STEAM Education, building upon the concepts of STEM and STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics).

STEM initially focused on fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills in learners. Over time, it expanded to include artistic skills, offering an interdisciplinary educational experience. Both these concepts have placed too much emphasis on materialistic progression, which may devalue humanity.

Dr. Munir Moosa raises the question, “Why do we constantly prioritize education that solely focuses on materialistic benefits? We are neglecting equity practices! We are producing nothing more than robots and aliens.”

According to Dr. Munir Moosa, “Education should go beyond knowledge acquisition and skill development. It should also foster a positive mindset, instill ethical values, and ensure active participation in equity practices. STEM and STEAM, if not implemented across disciplines with self-effacement, may suffocate humanity.”

Learners are not adequately taught about values in STEAM, which makes it challenging for them to navigate complex issues. Intellectual vanity, miscarriage of social justice, and materialistic greed may soon overpower human dignity due to negligence.

E-STEAM stresses respecting human values and dignity and making wise decisions across disciplines. The ethical dimension should be permeated across disciplines through value-based literacy. In this regard, STEAM must be initially scrutinized and contextually filtered to understand the existing content and nature, before infusing basic values. Also, teachers should avoid hammering ethical values, but rather guide learners to make the right choices in life and become resilient with time.